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Studies on the pH and Sorption of Basic Dyes on Alumina in Relation to Chromatography. Pt—II*

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PRETREATMENT of alumina with an alkali like sodium hydroxide frequently enhances its cation exchange capacity¹. In view of the above, the cationic dye, Janus red (C. I. 26115), was taken up to investigate its adsorption-desorption behaviour on alumina of varying pH (7.0-11.3). Galbraith *et al*² found the adsorption of Janus red (JR) on graphite to be dependent on the surface charge. Giles *et al*³ measured adsorption of the dye on a variety of solids and proposed ion-exchange.

Experimental

Alumina samples of pH 7.0-11.3 were prepared as described earlier¹, and their surface area determined (BET method).

Janus red (Gurr) was purified by repeated crystallization from ethanol-water (1 : 1 v/v), and dried at 50° for 8 hr. Projection area of the dye-ion was

estimated to be 227 Å² from 'Stuart-Briegleb' model. To minimise the adsorption effect of glass, the apparatus were rinsed with cetyl-trimethyl-ammonium bromide soln (1 g/l) and washed with water before use.

2.5-100 ml solutions were withdrawn from the stock solution of the dye in water (0.2 g/l), diluted to 100 ml and estimated colorimetrically at 505 nm with 'Spekol' spectrophotometer.

Adsorption experiments were conducted on alumina (0.25 g) with aqueous dye solutions of known concentration in 25 ml volumetric flasks. The flasks were immersed in thermostat, shaken periodically, 2 ml aliquot withdrawn after a specified period, centrifuged and estimated.

Adsorption vs time and temperature : The extent of adsorption from water as a function of time (10 min-24 hr) was studied with the substrate of pH 8.6-11.3 at 25 ± 1°. For this, the initial concentration of the dye solutions was 200, 100 and 20 mg/l. The results indicate the process to be slow with higher concentrations of the dye and fast at lower concentrations. Thus, at pH 10.6 (10 min) about 30% (200 mg/l) and 65% (20 mg/l) of the dye is adsorbed. The equilibrium is almost attained in 24 hr, although it takes 72 hr for higher dye concentrations. Temperature variation studies show the phenomenon to be endothermic (30-60°, pH 8.6-11.3, 4 hr), and the isosteric heats of adsorption (Q) is calculated to be 11-24 k cal/mole.

Adsorption vs pH : The change in the nature of adsorption with pH (7.0-11.5) was observed. The affinity of the solute gradually increases with increase in pH of the substrate and drops to zero at pH 7.0. The isotherms are of L₂-type and develop linear nature at pH 11.3.

Desorption studies : The reversibility of the dye adsorbed (25 ± 1° 24 hr, pH 8.6-11.3) was investigated with a number of organic solvent-water mixtures, CTA⁺-water (0.1% w/v) and aqueous inorganic electrolytes (10⁻² M NaCl and MgCl₂), as described earlier¹.

The desorption data reveal that the adsorption process is quite reversible. Thus, quantitative desorption occurs with dioxane-water (1 : 1) and *n*-butanol-ethanol-water (1 : 1 : 2). However, pyridine-water (1 : 4) and ethanol-water (1 : 1) desorb the dye completely at pH 8.6-9.5 and 8.6, respectively. Glycerol-water (1 : 4) and aqueous CTA⁺ also desorb 90% of the adsorbed dye. The Na⁺ ions have no effect, whereas Mg²⁺ ions are effective in removing the dye from the substrates. Precipitation of magnesium hydroxide occurs at pH > 10.6.

Results and Discussion

The adsorption is presumed to be essentially the same as that for anionic dyes on acid-treated alumina i.e., ion-exchange of dye-cations (simple or aggregated) with Na⁺ ions on the surface of alumina powder.

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Thus, high pH may enhance the apparent cation-exchange behaviour of the substrate. The molecule of JR is composed of complex aryl radical (colour-imparting ion) and the gegen-ion (chloride ion).

The results may be interpreted as follows :

(1) Time-variation data appear to show the adsorption to be a slow process. In the pH range 8.6-11.3, JR takes about 72 hr to achieve equilibrium. However, 25-30% adsorption takes place in 10 min (pH 10.0-10.6). The probable reason for such a behaviour may be the adsorption of large organic dye-cations which exist as aggregates of a number of ions or molecules in aqueous solution⁴. The presence of fine pores in the oxide may be causing slow penetration of the dye-species also.

(2) The variable heat of adsorption show the adsorption to be rather anomalous. As outlined above, a single reaction does not appear to be responsible for the 'Q' values. The apparent endothermic nature of adsorption may be due to association of the dye molecules⁵, which disaggregate at higher temperatures.

(3) The effective desorption of the dye by inorganic cation, Mg^{2+} , and the organic cation, CTA^+ , points to the ion-exchange nature of the process. pH titration studies⁶ on hydrated alumina have shown the material to be a mono-functional cation-exchanger. As compared to the univalent ions (e.g., Na^+), the higher capacity of the oxide for the polyvalent cations may be due to specific interactions or ionic repulsion.

The desorption behaviour with organic solvent-water mixtures is typical. It is likely that these desorbents may lower the surface tension or increase the solubility of the solute adsorbed. However, it needs further exploration.

(4) Flame photometric studies of the Na^+ ions released after adsorption of the dye on alumina showed an increase in the concentration of Na^+ ions at $\text{pH} > 9.5$. However, no change could be detected at $\text{pH} < 9.5$. This also indicates ion-exchange nature of adsorption.

The effect of the pretreatment of alumina with sodium hydroxide is simply to convert the oxide from the H^+ form to Na^+ form, and since this form is much lower than the H^+ form in the ion-selectivity series of oxides and hydrous oxides, displacement of Na^+ ions results in much more favourable equilibrium than that of the latter ion. Further, the ionically bound sodium content of alumina appears to decrease continuously with decreasing pH, becoming essentially negligible in acid range.

At high pH value, the H^+ ions of the >Al-OH of the substrate tend to dissociate from the oxygen, leaving a net negative charge on the surface, which will attract the dye cations. As the pH is lowered,

additional H^+ ions may associate with the $-\text{OH}$, leaving a positive charge on the surface.

Isotherms : The L-type of curves indicate monolayer. The steep nature of the isotherm at pH 11.3 may be due to gradual lodging of the dye cations into the micropores of the substrate.

The specific surface, S , (m^2/g), of the solid is given by the expression⁷ :

$$S = \gamma_m \times N \text{ a.}10^{-20}$$

Assuming flat orientation, if we consider the value of 'S' ($90 \pm 2 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$) and the projected area of the dye ion (227 \AA^2), the γ_m for the dye is calculated to be 6.7×10^{-6} mole/g at pH 11.0. The actual amount of the dye adsorbed is considerably higher as compared to the above value, suggesting association of the dye cations as charged micelles.

Chromatographic separation :

Synthetic mixtures of the two dyes, Janus red and Ethyl violet (EV) were separated on alumina column. The two characteristic observations utilised in the separation are varying degree of adsorption of the dyes on the adsorbent and differential migration with desorbents.

Method I : Quick-fit glass column ($10 \times 1 \text{ cm}$) was packed dry with alumina of pH 8.6 (8 g ; 5 cm). 5.0 ml aqueous solution of each of the two dyes (80 mg/l) were withdrawn, mixed, applied to the column and kept as such for 2 hr. On developing the chromatogram with 3 ml of dioxane-water (1 : 1), two distinct bands could be seen, upper red band of JR (0.5 cm), colourless space (0.5 cm) followed by violet band of EV (1.0 cm). The violet zone was eluted out of the column with 5 ml of the eluent.

The JR zone (1.5 cm) could be desorbed on elution with 5 ml of the eluent. The % recovery of the dyes is 99.9 (EV) and 99.7 (JR).

Method II : It has been observed that JR adsorbed on basic alumina (pH 8.6-10.6) has no desorption affinity with aqueous sodium chloride, whereas EV is desorbed considerably. This fact, along with the varying degree of adsorption of the two dyes on alumina of pH 9.5 has been utilised for the present separation.

The dye mixture was added to the column ($10 \times 1 \text{ cm}$) packed with alumina of pH 9.5 (9.5 g ; 6 cm), and kept for 2 hr. Aqueous sodium chloride ($10^{-2} M$) was gradually added as eluting solvent. Two distinct bands, separated from each other (0.8 cm), were seen on the addition of the eluent (2 ml). EV was eluted out with 25 ml of the eluent. The JR band retained at the top of the adsorbent was removed on washing with 20 ml of pyridine-water (1 : 4). The recovery is 99.6%.

Method -III: The dye combination was also separated on an alumina column of pH 10.6, (8 g ; 5 cm). After 2 hr, the mixed chromatogram was eluted with NaCl (10^{-3} M) and EV could pass out of the column with 40 ml of the eluent. On further irrigation with 20 ml of *n*-butanol-ethanol-water (1 : 1 : 2, v/v), the retained dye (JR) was eluted out.

It may, therefore, be said that alumina, after chemical pretreatment, can be converted into an useful chromatographic material, which, of course, needs a close adsorption-desorption study of the solutes.

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Utilization of Lime Dust and Lime Sludge— An Industrial Waste

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INDUSTRIES offer a number of bye-products and waste materials which can be utilized for useful purposes. Amongst the various wastes produced in a steel plant, lime dust and lime sludge have been studied in the present investigation. It is estimated that about 2000 metric tons of the above two waste materials are available every year from Rourkela Steel Plant alone. During the process of production of lime from the lime calcining plant, lots of lime fines below 5 mm size, commonly known as lime dust are produced. Lime sludge is obtained when calcium carbide is treated with water for the manufacture of acetylene gas. Both lime dust and lime sludge are waste materials as far as a steel plant is

concerned. It was therefore thought worthwhile to study whether these can be utilized for producing bleaching powder and gypsum, thereby conserving lime stone deposits for better use in cement and steel industries¹. Further, the utilization of these wastes will also increase the overall economy of the steel production.

Experimental

Preparation of bleaching powder : Experiments were planned to prepare bleaching powder from lime dust and lime sludge. Since lime sludge is moist, it was dried before use. The amount of CaCO_3 present in the sludge sample was negligibly small (nearly 1%) and hence prior ignition was not necessary. An adequate amount of the dried sample was taken in a conical flask and chlorine gas was passed over it with constant stirring. The formation of bleaching powder from lime and chlorine is an exothermic process and so the temperature was maintained constant round about 35° by circulating cold water round the reaction vessel. The reaction was complete in 30-40 min.

Fig. Flow sheet-preparation of bleaching powder.

The amount of available chlorine was estimated from a small amount of the sample each time following the standard method². The estimations were repeated at 15 days intervals for a period of 3 months to ascertain the storage capacity. The above experiments on preparation of bleaching powder and testing were carried out using other lime sources like sea shell lime, natural clinkers, and impure and low grade lime stone mineral available in Ganjam district of Orissa. The results are reported in Tables 1-3.

Preparation of gypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) : Lime wastes can be converted into gypsum either by treatment with $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ or by treatment with dil H_2SO_4 .

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF DIFFERENT LIME SOURCES

Constituent	Lime dust	Lime sludge	Sea shell lime	Natural clinker	
				No. 1	No. 2
CaO	80.0	56.6	62.2	57.5	56.8
SiO ₂	1.8	4.6	0.8	5.5	12.8
Al ₂ O ₃	1.5	Traces	Traces	Traces	Traces
Fe ₂ O ₃	1.5	2.0	nil	6.7	5.0
MgO	2.5	0.8	2.0	1.0	1.0
Loss on ignition	8.2	33.0	34.2	27.6	24.0